

STRESS AND ALTRUISM IN PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY

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Abstract: The article highlights specific psychological aspects of professional stress and altruism. We know that humanity lives and works surrounded by stressful factors. Pedagogical activity is full of stressful factors as it is a professional activity in the "human-human" system. This article analyzes the professional stress that occurs in pedagogical activities and their psychological characteristics. Altruistic principles in pedagogical activities and their impact on overcoming professional stress are psychologically analyzed, and based on empirical data, conclusions and recommendations are made.

Keywords: stress, professional stress, pedagogical activity, altruism, rational altruism, pedagogue, sociability.

I. INTRODUCTION. The acceleration of the rhythm of modern life has led to a significant increase in the physical, mental, emotional load on a person, due to everyday problems, interpersonal relationships, the content of professional activity, information overload. Quite often, a person has to be in a state of emotional stress, experience a feeling of heightened anxiety, anxiety, self-doubt, and also experience the so-called stress. Such states are often accompanied not only by mental imbalance, but also by a number of negative changes in the functioning of physiological mechanisms in the human body, and this affects the performance of a specialist. According to statistics from Research & Branding Group in 2018, 17% of stress in human life is caused by occupational activities [5]. According to the World Labor Organization, occupational stress is very popular in Japan. There are even deaths among workers as a result of chronic occupational stress, with 35% of the population blaming occupational stress for their health problems [5]. Therefore, a number of scientific studies are being conducted by psychologists and medical staff on the prevention of stress and its consequences. In particular, the World Health Organization (WHO) has drafted the 13th General Action Plan for 2019-2023: strengthening the health of the population, maintaining peace in the world, coverage of public services. The work carried out by the experts of the International Association for Stress Management in the framework of the project "Negative mental

stress and stress in the workplace" is aimed at overcoming mental disorders and stress.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW. Let's talk about stress and its psychological properties. Stress is derived from the English word "stress", a set of abnormal adaptive reactions of the body to various adverse factors. Initially, the concept of "stress" was explained in physiology as a non-specialized reaction of the organism in response to various unpleasant impressions. It was later used to express the individual's physiological, psychological, and behavioral state in emergencies. The essence of stress in psychology was first described by G. Sele. G. Sele distinguishes three stages of stress as an adaptation syndrome:

1. Anxiety reaction;
2. Resistance phase;
3. Voltage stage.

Anxiety reactions occur at the first exposure to stressors. In a short time the level of resistance of the organism decreases, somatic and vegetative functions are impaired. After that, the organism uses its reserve resources and the body's self-regulatory mechanisms are activated. If the defense mechanism is effective, the anxiety disappears and the body returns to normal activity. If an effective psychological defense mechanism is not selected, the next stage of resistance is moved.

The resistance phase occurs as a result of the continuous action of stressors and triggers a protective reaction that supports the body. In this case, a balanced distribution of adaptation reserves occurs on the basis of the external manifestation of stress in the functional system. In the stage of resistance, resentment and resentment in the person begin in the second stage. At this stage, the body begins to use the available power in reserve. However, it is known that human physiological and mental capabilities are limited. As a result, if the effects of stress continue, the person has no strength to resist it, and the psyche begins to "retreat" and positive emotions to negative ones.

The stress phase represents a violation of the body's protective adaptive mechanisms that counteract the effects of excessive and continuous stressors. Adaptive reserves are significantly reduced. Failure to reduce the level of stressors in humans leads to a sharp decrease in the level of resistance to stress. At the same time, there are specific changes in human cognitive processes, disorders associated with the inability to process information. In the phase of tension, two changes can be observed in human behavior: in the first, chaos and impulsiveness increase in a person's behavior, and in the second, the opposite, that is, a person begins to try to "escape reality." The destructive state as a result of stressogenic effects is characterized not by a decrease in human activity efficiency, but by its general impairment [4].

Professional stress factors manifested in pedagogical activities can be conditionally divided into the following groups:

- factors related to labor activity: excessive workload, poor working conditions, lack of time;

- stress factors related to the role of the pedagogue in the pedagogical team: inability to fulfill professional obligations, lack of recognition in the team, everyone assuming his responsibility, uncertainty resulting from unfair distribution of workload, extremely low responsibility to the team, low participation in team life;

- factors related to interpersonal relations in the pedagogical team: destructive relations with leaders, colleagues, students, parents, communication problems;

- factors related to pedagogical career: professional "failure", fear of retirement, insufficient professional knowledge; professional

- external factors: family problems, chronic diseases, etc. [3].

The development of occupational stress is highlighted as an actual scientific problem of the current period, which is related to the work of employees, work productivity, work efficiency and quality, as well as the impact on the health of employees [7]. At the same time, today's research on stress related to the labor process in the literature is not adequately systematized both at the conceptual level and in defining the boundaries of the subject [8]. This, in turn, creates great difficulties for modern researchers. Currently, it is very difficult to distinguish professional stress from other types of stress described in the literature, so it is customary to distinguish several types of stress that are related to the professional activity of a person in one way or another [7]. They are as follows:

- work stress (job stress) and work stress (work stress) - types of stress caused by the conditions of work and specific features of a specific position;

- professional stress (occupational stress) arising from the specific characteristics of the work content and professional environment;

- organizational stress (organizational stress), which takes into account the ability of the employees of the organization to adapt to the conditions of collective work related to the tensions that destroy the effective functioning of the organization;

- informational stress - stress related to problems in processing the flow of information in the process of activity;

- stress at the workplace is a concept arising from professional and organizational stress, which means the physical and mental strain associated with being at the workplace.

So, stress is an integral part of work. It can occur under the influence of various stress factors that have a negative effect on a person. The study of methods and mechanisms of human adaptation to professional activity (including professional deformation) is directly related to the problem of stress. The scope of the study of occupational stress is very wide, so it is impossible to single out a universally recognized concept of occupational stress.

2 different factors play a major role in the occurrence of occupational stress:

1. Level of employment;

2. Leader's support.

The more actively a person starts work, the more he is supported by the manager and the team, the less stress is given to him.

Another factor causing occupational stress is the untimeliness of work. Working more than 50 hours a week leads to heart disease. Timeliness of work is observed in service workers.

One of the characteristics of professional activities is lack of time. As the last days of the month approach, the stress arousal level has been seen to rise several times during the reporting period. Occupational stress can also be influenced by individual characteristics of a person. The most common of them are:

- health indicator factor;
- level of professional ability;
- personality type and its direction (to itself, to others, to activity).

It is necessary to take into account the above during recruitment and retraining. A healthy person, calm in his professional abilities, good-willed, activity-oriented person is not prone to professional stress or easily overcomes stress. A person with opposite qualities is prone to professional stress.

In the psychological encyclopedia of R. Corsini and A. Auerbach, occupational stress is determined as a result of the interaction of people and the work they do. The obtained result reflects the occurrence of changes that prevent people from performing normal activities [4].

A. B. Leonova in her works describes professional stress as a condition that arises as a response to professional difficulties and demands [9].

Social psychologist Christina Maslach defined occupational stress as a comprehensive phenomenon. According to him, stress is manifested in the physical and mental reactions of a person during work.

J. Sharit and G. Salvendy defined occupational stress as a multidimensional phenomenon and emphasized that it is expressed in physiological and psychological reactions to complex working conditions [5].

This approach, according to A.N. Zankovsky, allows to identify the following areas of stress study [6]:

- a) determining which parameters of this phenomenon correspond to the type of labor activity under consideration;
- b) to determine the "desired areas" (in terms of subjective and objective reactions of the worker) of each of the investigated dimensions;
- c) standardizing the deviations to correlate the responses in each studied dimension;
- g) to determine the "weight" (share) of each studied measure.

S. Kasl defines two main directions of interpretation of the concept of "stress at work":

- 1) In a narrow sense, stress is excessive demands of the environment in relation to a person's ability, that is, the amount of work at a level that a person cannot perform, excessiveness, excessive motivation, stimulation, and the like;

- 2) In a broader sense, stress is the inconsistency of relations in the integrated system of "person - environment".

This system includes not only the above review, but also the relationship between human needs and the possibility of their satisfaction at work (in other words, not using human potential, reduced workload, low level of stimulation).

At this point, it should be said that this is largely related to the problem of justice in the field of work (the contribution should match the incentive), and this problem is directly related to the problem of self-esteem of the employee [9].

According to many scholars, the central concept in the literature on occupational stress is the concept of "control" (that is, assessment and correction).

In R.A. Karasik's scientific works devoted to the creation of a general theory of stress in the workplace, the following hypothesis was put forward on the basis of research devoted to the study of control problems: stress is caused by the interaction between two factors, that is, responsibility and control ("work breadth" and "psychological demands"). originates. High-stress jobs (occupations) have such types of work (occupation) in which an individual with great responsibility cannot adequately control the methods and results of tasks. "Active" professions make great demands on a person, and also require the implementation of a high level of control (doctors, teachers, lawyers, managers), the author believes. There are also professions with a high level of control, but with relatively low requirements (or delayed requirements): scientists, architects, repairmen. These occupations are considered to be the least stressful. Passive occupations (guards, janitors) provide little opportunity for control and make low psychological demands on the employee [13]. As a result, the higher the social demands, the greater the stress.

The various approaches that we have analyzed above have analyzed the factors that cause occupational stress. Together with these scientists, models have been developed that shed light on the psychological mechanisms of occupational stress.

According to V.A. Bodrov, the most famous of the many models of occupational stress is the Michigan model (and its variants). This model was created at the Institute for Social Research at the University of Michigan in the United States. This model, reflecting the stress caused by the social environment, reflects the characteristics of human perception of environmental factors and its reactions, as well as the possible consequences of this situation on human health [5]. Individual differences and elements of the social environment can modify these relationships.

Another model of occupational stress was proposed by Mac Gras. According to this model, the source of stress is an objective (real) situation, as in the social environment model. This situation is perceived as subjectively reflected through its evaluation mechanism. This assessment leads to the stage of decision-making about the manifestation of a specific reaction. Reactions are mainly behavioral, physiological and psychological reactions are not combined (as in the social environment model), but are manifested as conscious behavior. Although these two models are compatible with each other, they differ in the type of final results.

According to T. Koch, the professional stress model includes:

- 1) requirements for an individual;
- 2) individual characteristics, skills and general abilities related to adaptation to requirements (personal resources);

- 3) situational constraints affecting the adaptation process;
- 4) external support.

The absolute level of demands is not decisive for the emergence of stress. The most important thing is the discrepancy between demand levels and personal resources. Such a level of inconsistency can create conditions for the development of stress or only functional activity (strain), or in its significant amounts [6].

The general model of professional stress is reflected in the works of M. Smith and P. Karayan. This model reflects the content of occupational stress and the interdependence of its main components [13].

In general, work system factors can lead to proper stress reactions, which are moderated by personal and cognitive characteristics. If these short-term stress reactions become chronic, they can have many negative consequences for health and work performance.

All models of occupational stress have in common that the authors tried to define the content of stress. This is mainly done by parameters that can be recorded.

In this regard, as N.I. Naenko noted, these indicators can be divided into two approaches to study.

The first approach is based on a direct comparison of the psychological characteristics of the human condition with physiological indicators and work efficiency.

The second approach is based on the study of the nature of psychological stress, the patterns of manifestation of one or another external reaction, which is considered as a determinant of psychological and mental processes [8].

A brief analysis of various theories and models of occupational stress shows that each of them takes into account some aspect of the multifaceted problem.

For a deeper understanding of this phenomenon, it is necessary to further improve separate theoretical positions, as well as a very important issue, to combine, compare and analyze them.

The appearance of stress is determined by the influence of extreme factors related to the composition, organization, and conditions of the activity on the individual.

Extreme situations are divided into short-term and long-term types. In the short term, the reaction programs that are always "ready" in a person are activated. Long-term extreme situations require adaptive restructuring of human functional systems. In this case, reconstruction can cause subjective unpleasant feelings and have a negative impact on health [7].

Under short-term strong extreme effects, various signs of stress are clearly manifested. Short-term stress is the intensive use of the "surface" flexible resource and the simultaneous activation of the "deep" resource. If the "surface" resources are not enough to meet the extreme demands of the environment, and if the speed of mobilization of "deep" resources to compensate for the expenditure is low, the "deep" adaptive reserve may die, despite the fact that the "deep" adaptive reserve remains unexploited [9].

V.L.Marishuk and V.I.Evdokimov describe short-term stress, sudden acceleration of pulse and breathing, rhythm disturbance, sweating, pupil diameter, sudden changes in motor reactions on the face, acute experience, etc. mentioned [13].

Long-term stress in activity is characterized by the gradual mobilization and consumption of "surface" and "deep" adaptation capabilities [6]. Given that the impact of stress on human mental and physical health can lead to destructive situations, its elimination or prevention poses enormous challenges for psychologists today. The role of coping-behavioral strategies in the formation of stress resilience in psychology is sufficiently highlighted.

Coping-behavioral strategies serve as a mechanism of psychological protection in overcoming psychological stresses. Psychological sources distinguish three components of coping-behavioral strategies: cognitive, emotional, and behavioral.

Cognitive coping strategies: ignoring, humility, dissimulation, maintaining self-control, problem analysis, relativity, religiosity, confusion, giving meaning, setting one's own value.

Emotional coping strategies: protest, emotional relaxation, optimism, passive cooperation, humility, self-accusation, aggressiveness.

Behavioral coping strategies: distraction, altruism, active avoidance, compensation, constructive activity, retreat, cooperation, conversion.

We have today addressed the behavioral component of a co-opting strategy in highlighting the role of altruism in overcoming personal stressors. It is in the behavioral component of the coping-behavior strategy that altruism manifests itself as a coping-resource that helps a person cope with stress. That's altruism, a person's ability to value and respect the people around him, their interests and values, as well as building a favorable relationship based on mutual assistance. Proper development of this coping resource reduces the risk of depression and increased anxiety, and also contributes to successful adaptation to stress.

Altruism is the behavior of a person who is focused on the interests of another person or social group and has no interest. The term altruism was first used by the French philosopher O. Conte as an anti-egoism term [3].

Altruism acts as the basis for the socio-psychological manifestation of humane relations, which are expressed in such external forms of behavior as care, generosity, help and support of their comrades. The mechanisms of manifestation of altruism, depending on the attitudes of the personality, are different. Acts of altruism, determined by situational attitudes, are actualized through actions in specific stressful situations, such as, for example, saving a comrade at the cost of one's life. Or, in the light of the semantic attitude, altruism becomes a conscious value orientation, which determines the behavior of the individual as a whole and turns into the meaning of his life. The real significance of the altruistic behavior of a person is determined by the nature of those values that underlie his relationships with people. The feeling of the "shoulder of a comrade", faith in love and support from others, who make up the interpersonal and supra-personal group resource of a person, are able to mobilize and actualize his volitional resource.

From this point of view, altruism as a psychological phenomenon embodies the aspiration of the individual to perfection and the actions of empathy, kindness and benevolence to overcome tensions in interpersonal relationships, to give up something for others. But altruism manifests itself in a person's behavior in a uniquely individual way. Accordingly, the following types of altruism are distinguished in psychological sources:

Altruism, which results from feelings of sympathy and empathy, is altruistic behavior that results from compassion for others. This is more likely to occur as a result of a sense of emotional attachment to relatives, close people.

Moral altruism is the part that acts as an "internal censorship" of the individual. This is more likely to be related to a person's inner moral institutions and conscience, beliefs.

Self-sacrifice is characterized by the self-sacrifice of a person, and there are two sides to it: the positive side gives a bounty to a person who is valuable to him, and the negative side gives up on himself.

Rational altruism is an attempt to find a balance that does not harm one's own interests and the interests of others. Every altruistic movement that is performed is observed.

F. Assizsky, who made an in-depth analysis of individual views on altruism, analyzed several manifestations of the manifestation of altruism in the person [7]:

The parental view is that it is unique to all humanity and involves a parent taking care of their child. This condition can also be called "parental instinct". In some cases, this instinct is also characterized by self-sacrifice.

Mutual assistance is the act of helping someone without expecting the same help from them. This type of altruism is observed among close relatives, true friends and lovers. These actions are often influenced by norms and social expectations.

In this form of moral altruism, a person simply acts on the principle of "doing good" to others, and this is ingrained in his system of values. We often refer to this category of individuals as volunteers.

Demonstration is an altruistic behavior that is performed in order to assert one's social status in public.

Compassion is an altruistic attempt made because of emotional sensitivity and strong reflection on people.

G. Spencer distinguishes 2 types of altruism: "Justice is a social activity that is important for maintaining social balance in society. Charity is the act of voluntarily reaching out to others." [4]

Altruism in a person as a psychological phenomenon is associated with certain altruistic emotional experiences, attitudes, and personality orientations that govern a person's behavior. According to BI Dodonov, in order for a person to develop an innate tendency to altruism, he first exhibits altruistic emotional experiences. This situation leads to the formation of an altruistic position in the person, the full understanding of this process by the person leads to an altruistic orientation in the person [5].

It also helps reduce stress levels, according to psychologists at Yale University. A study by Emily Ansell and her colleagues found that over a two-week period, several dozen adults, ages 18 to 44, reported their emotional state and what good they did in terms of helping others in a day. ... In an article published in *Clinical Psychological Science*, the authors write that in those days when a person often helped someone, the helping person's mood improved, and in response to stress, he had less emotional "negativity."

Altruism did not have to be some kind of large-scale, it was enough to help someone figure out how to get to the desired street, or to hold the elevator for someone who did not have time to enter it, to pick up something that someone dropped, etc.

There are specific aspects of the manifestation of altruism as a psychological defense mechanism in overcoming psychological stresses, the following types of which are classified by E.P. Ilin:

1. Altruistic dependence;
2. Rationalization of behavior and attitudes.

Altruistic dependence. In such a situation, the person projects his egoistic impulses by caring for other people and tries to satisfy his own needs regardless of the fate of others. Here, when the internal conflict between the needs of "I want, but I can not have" causes stress in the person, this psychological defense mechanism begins to manifest itself in the form of coping-behavioral strategies. For example, a person who is jealous of himself because of his miserliness becomes very generous to those close to him. In this case, the effect of psycho-emotional stressors on the person is reduced by the fact that the altruist's personal "I" replaces the analogous "I" of another person. The main reason for this is that the main stress factor is the needs in the personal self, which are not realized under the influence of social norms, national mental characteristics or upbringing. As a result, when similar needs arise in another person, the person tries to satisfy his needs through his own selfish desires and reduces the influence of stressogenic factors on the psyche.

Behavioral and behavioral rationalization. Rationalization is a protective mechanism aimed at giving a logical explanation to human behavior in order to hide the original motives. In doing so, the person creates internal stability and believes in these "logical explanations". In such a situation, the altruist takes on the role of a human being who actively intervenes in the destiny of others. At the heart of such altruistic behavior, in fact, is the need to strive to control everything so that no one threatens the personal self. This psychological defense mechanism strengthens the subjective internal local control in a person, allows for voluntary schematic and rational interpretation of the situation in order to feel inner calm and control over the situation. Emotional experiences are hidden by a strong desire to analyze the situation logically. This reduces the effects of stress factors [2].

In addition, the factors that influence the manifestation of altruism in the form of stress-overcoming behavior also vary. They are:

Cognitive factors are factors that help people to reduce the impact of stressors by learning about their worldview, learning, and gaining personal skills and

experience. We can use Rowell Hezmann's "Cognitive Scenario Model". According to Rauell Hezmann's "Cognitive Scenario Model", a person is taught to help others and to perceive social reality without exaggerating negative emotions. Emotional disturbances in a person are prevented by transferring the person's cognitions related to the emotional assessment of reality to the feelings of "caring, helping".

Social factors are factors related to the desire to become a member of society and feel group support. The role of social influences in the life of the individual and society is incomparable. It is social interactions, i.e., social norms, sanctions, a sense of social responsibility, and the interaction of social roles that trigger a tendency in people to stress, and these stresses are reduced by performing altruistic behaviors under the influence of social factors. At the same time, the "sense of social need" in the person helps to avoid the negative effects of various stressogenic effects.

Psychological factors are a set of factors associated with the psychological protection of the personal "I" (getting rid of guilt), increasing self-esteem, self-control, self-confidence, self-esteem. Psychological factors in turn lead to internal conflicts and stress. However, if feelings such as psychological protection of the self, self-esteem, self-control, self-confidence are formed in a positive way through the development of altruistic motives, then this condition in itself serves to increase the level of resistance to stress [1].

III. THEORY AND METHODOLOGY. The health of teaching staff and the effectiveness of their pedagogical activities, like many professional fields, depend on the working conditions, the environment in the team, and professional functional tasks. However, many studies have shown that in the last decade, the number of stress factors associated with pedagogical activity is increasing. Today, the activity of pedagogues is full of psychogenic, intellectual and emotional stress. In fact, daily reports, issues related to coaching activities, involvement in public works, problems related to leader-employee relations in the team of pedagogues do not leave time for pedagogues to engage in pedagogical creativity, which is the cause of mental and physical fatigue and stress in them.

When British scientists researched the relationship between stress and professional activity, they listed 22 professions that are prone to the most stressful factors. The "proud third" place among the stress-prone professions belongs to the teaching profession.

The teaching profession is one of the professions prone to stressful factors that require self-control and management. Continuous changes in the requirements for pedagogical activity, influx of new information flow and lack of time for its assimilation, emotional and social tension in pedagogical activity complicate the conditions of professional activity and cause an increase in stress among pedagogues. Taking this into account, we set ourselves the goal of determining the manifestation of professional stress in pedagogues.

In our research, we have organized our work by approaching the principles of determinism and systematicity.

It is known that the principle of determinism (Lat.determinare-to determine, to require) implies that the phenomena of the material and spiritual world are

objectively legally interrelated and require each other. Based on this principle, the idea of causation is such that there is such a relationship between various events that, in the case of such a relationship, when the appropriate conditions exist, it constitutes the idea that some event will constantly cause another event [11]. The realization of the principle of determinism in our dissertation research is carried out by assuming that the emergence of professional stress based on a specific mechanism and its representation (appearance) in a certain form is always the result of a certain level of influence of some social, cognitive and affectogenic factors. is increased.

As a methodological principle of scientific research, the principle of systematicity requires the study of the researched objects and phenomena as a system, which explains the characteristics of the phenomena with the characteristics of the interaction of the elements that make them up. This principle requires the analysis of the subject of scientific research to distinguish the elements that make it up as a system and the structural functional connections between them, to justify the levels of the system and the factors that make up the system [10]. The principle of systematicity envisages implementation of the mechanism of manifestation of professional stress in pedagogues from the point of view of systemic harmony. In addition, the results obtained from the experimental tests carried out within the framework of our research clearly show the combined state of the manifestation of professional stress.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL WORK. One of the main reasons why we chose the audience of pedagogues as an experimental base is the high level of moral students involved in pedagogical activities and the high emotional load.

308 pedagogues of general secondary education school No. 304 in Sergeli district of Tashkent city, No. 4-24 in Pas Dargom district of Samarkand region, No. 10-27 in Pop district of Namagan region participated in the research.

Initially, we administered the Occupational Stress Scale (developed by D. Fontan) in order to divide our subjects into experimental and control groups. "The results of the occupational stress scale were analyzed quantitatively and qualitatively. The results of the quantitative analysis were presented in the form of a table and a histogram.

Table 1

Features of the manifestation of professional stress in teachers

Name of scales	Results of the testers
Low level of occupational stress	47.1%;
Medium level of occupational stress	50.6%
High level of occupational stress	2.3%

From the above table, we can see that 2.3% of the test subjects have a high level of professional stress, that is, they have a low level of workability and high emotional stress.

According to A.S. Shafronova, the profession of pedagogue always requires work on oneself, focused on the content of the activity. A large amount of

information flow in the work of a pedagogue and high social demands placed on a pedagogue are stressogenic factors.

The high level of professional stress in our test subjects can be explained as follows: perception and processing of information received through communication with colleagues, students and their parents, uncertainty in social roles (resulting from excessive workload on public affairs), the large number of assigned tasks and the inability to fulfill them. as a result of the short duration of the training, the pedagogue cannot allocate his time properly.

The high level of professional stress in teachers is characterized by the intensity of the workload, the complexity and number of assigned tasks, the strength of cognitive stress and social control, problems in interpersonal relationships, emotional stress, physical discomfort, and even the pedagogue's feeling bad.

The average level of occupational stress was found in 50.6% of the subjects. This indicator is related to the absence of free time as a result of teachers being buried in full-time work, the unhealthy atmosphere in the pedagogical team, the low level of professional training of the pedagogue or the high level of excessive responsibility for the assigned task.

A low level of professional stress was found in 47.1% of subjects. These examinees have important professional qualities for pedagogues, i.e., empathy, erudition, pedagogical thinking, intuition, ability to improvise, observation, optimism, reflection, internal motivation and a high need for self-development, which reduces the tendency of pedagogues to professional stress and ensures that they get out of stressful situations wisely.

Our respondents with a high and average level of occupational stress made up the experimental group. This means stress related to the professional process in our subjects, that is, incompatibility of relations in the integrated system of "person - environment". This situation includes the relationship between human needs and the possibility of satisfying them at work (in other words, not using human potential, reduced workload, low level of stimulation). At this point it is worth saying that this is largely related to the problem of fairness in the field of work (contribution should match the incentive), and this problem is directly related to the problem of self-esteem of the employee. In general, the high level of susceptibility to occupational stress can be related to many factors.

At the next stage, in order to determine the motivation of altruistic behavior in the team of pedagogues, we conducted the diagnostic methodology of "Altruism-Egoism" personal attitudes. The methodology for diagnosing "altruism-egoism" personality disorders was conducted in the testers, and the obtained results were analyzed in terms of quantity and quality. The results of the quantitative analysis were presented in the form of a table.

Table 2

Aspects related to altruistic attitudes of occupational stress in teachers

Scales	Low level of occupational stress	Medium level of occupational stress	High level of occupational stress
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Altruistic dispositions in a person	52,5%	42,1%	5,4%
Egoistic attitudes in the person	15,1%	30,4%	54,5%

V. DISCUSSION. As can be seen from the results, 52.5% of teachers with a low level of professional stress have high levels of altruistic attitudes. This situation is determined by the fact that the rational altruism of pedagogues is manifested at the level of professional training. Rational altruism is determined by a person's level of reflexive empathy, high emotional intelligence. For this reason, among our respondents, pedagogues with a low level of professional stress were also observed to have high altruistic attitudes. This situation indicates the psycho-emotional maturity of the person and indicates his emotional stagnation.

5.1% of our respondents with a low level of professional stress were found to be connected with egoistic attitudes. If we analyze this situation from the psychological point of view of altruism, egoism is manifested in this category of pedagogues as a special form of protecting the "I" of the individual.

In 42.1% of our respondents, there was a positive correlation between the medium level of professional stress and altruistic attitudes. In this case, it was determined that the system of moral values, social perception in working with children, social identification in the system of interpersonal relations, and altruistic attitudes in pedagogues are manifested as a feature that provides stability to stress in connection with the professional activity of pedagogues. In 30.4% of our respondents of this category, the high level of egoistic attitudes is determined by the desire of pedagogues to act in accordance with the students of the society and the need to emphasize the ego due to the high motivation of striving for success in the activity. This condition is also manifested as a psychological protection mechanism of the individual.

The high level of professional stress in 5.4% of our respondents changes proportionally with increasing professional stress, since altruistic attitudes are often associated with the desire for social approval. In 54.5% of the respondents, the predominance of egoistic institutions confirms this situation once again.

VI. CONCLUSION. Based on the above analytical data, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- stress can affect the psychophysiological and functional state of a person and lead to various negative consequences;
- the role of coping behavior in reducing and eliminating the negative effects of stress, as it manifests itself as a syndrome of adaptation;
- by helping others, a person can alleviate the emotional stress associated with stress.

Based on empirical data, we recommend the following in order to prevent professional stress in pedagogical activities:

For educators:

1. pedagogues work on themselves, increase the level of professional competence and follow the agenda;
2. using autogenic and relaxation exercises once a day;
3. to get rid of the feeling of fatigue in the body with physical exercises after a day of mental work;
4. striving to be in a constructive position in interpersonal relations;
5. making good use of relaxation and felicitological functions of the family, and of course performing laughter therapy at the end of the day.

For the leaders of the pedagogical team:

1. proper organization of work (that is, full observance of working hours and rest hours) in order to protect human resources in the pedagogical team;
2. conducting in-depth activities within the framework of mental health in order to strengthen the psychological service in education in order to ensure the psycho-emotional health of pedagogues who are labor subjects;
3. allocating work to employees taking into account pedagogical seniority and age characteristics;
4. spiritual and material stimulation of the activities of pedagogues;
5. regular organization of psychological training aimed at improving the social and psychological climate in the team and forming a sanogenic mindset among pedagogues;
6. taking into account that not being able to organize time correctly is also a stressogenic factor, it is recommended to develop training programs and organize special training courses on the subject of "Time management" for pedagogues to improve the efficiency of time management and its use.

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